

MEDIA LITERACY

ACADEMIC MEDIA LITERACY AND THE ROLE OF UNIVERSITIES

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ABSTRACT: Since tertiary education is the highest level of the sequentially structured formal education system, one can argue that universities should help their students to achieve the highest levels of literacy. In this sense, academic literacy comprises all skills necessary to competently read and write academic texts. Comparing different information and communication technologies in a historic perspective, it becomes obvious that digital media create new media formats and academic genres. Academic media literacy therefore could be interpreted as the competence to critically use and produce new types of academic artefacts. To be able to teach and train these skills, universities have to become more aware of the requirements of scholarly media use and media production.

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Introduction

Historically speaking, media education and the notion of media literacy emerged in the 20th century, as a reaction to the success of audio-visual media, such as records and film, and their electronically distributed equivalents, broadcasts in radio and television. Largely, media education at that time had a rather culture-pessimistic tendency at that time, mainly trying to defend the consumers of audio-visual media products against the incalculable influences, dangers and information overflows created by media, which - at that time - were 'new'. On the other hand, audio-visual media never had a big influence on formal education. Even if students spent more and more of their lifetime in front of radios or television sets, the use of audio-visual media in the classroom did not become integral part of the daily routine in formal education, and education via radio or television remained a rather peripheral matter. As a result, media education (understood merely as the training in the responsible consumption of non-academic audio-visual media products) remained a nice to have add on to formal education.

The emergence of digital media, the differentiation of digital media formats and the explosive proliferation of digital media products, but also the obvious impact of digital media on formal education makes it necessary to reconsider this traditional notion of media literacy and the significance for media education. For this purpose, the following chapters deal with the general importance of literacy in formal, especially in higher education, analyze the impact of new, digital media on academic literacy, and

discuss the role of higher education institutions in contributing to the development of academic literacy.

Literacy at an academic level

To understand the relevance of digital media for formal education, it is helpful to understand first the impact of other than audio-visual information and communication media, namely the impact of script and print. For this purpose, we draw on the comparison of different information and communication technologies in the works of Niklas Luhmann that has been summarized by Berghaus (2004).

Print as prerequisite of formal education

It is obvious that print and the ubiquitous availability of printed media products was an essential prerequisite for the emergence of a formal education system that has become accessible (and compulsory) for the entire population. Print allowed for the comprehensive inclusion into the education system at least at the level of primary and secondary education, and for mass enrollments in tertiary (higher) education, even if these long-term effects only emerged in the 20th century. This delay can be attributed to the fact that society needs some time to make appropriate use of the additional communication potential provided by new technologies. E.g. Nentwich (2001) explained that the first university presses emerged in the late 15th century only, and the first academic journals were founded as late as in the 17th century. Similarly, it took some time to see the general potential for obligatory schooling of the masses and even longer to translate this idea into political action for its implementation.

Alphabetization as core of formal education

However, the use of script and print is not just a constitutive requirement of formal education. Rather, it is its centerpiece. Alphabetization, the teaching and learning of skills for reading and writing, is the core of formal education. For sure, content matters as well, be it the broad body of knowledge regarded as relevant for general education, or be it the deep knowledge in a specific field that characterizes specialist training. Nevertheless, being literate does not require knowledge about specific content, but the generic skills to consume media products by reading and understanding, and to produce new media products by writing new texts¹.

Alphabetization at an academic level

If this is true, what does literacy have to do with higher education? Is not alphabetization a clear task of primary, maybe of secondary education, while higher education can distance itself from this task and just focus on disciplinary content and specialist training? Many university professors probably would favor this answer, delegating the unloved task of alphabetization to the lower ranks in the educational hierarchy.

¹ This is a crucial difference to the notion of media literacy in the context of audio-visual media. Due to technical and economic reasons, the production and dissemination of audio-visual media products tends to be much more centralized and unidirectional. Most of the participants in audio-visual communication are restricted to the role of consumers. Consequently, media education in the field of audio-visual communication predominantly focuses on the informed consumption of media products.

TABLE 1. COMPARING INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES,
BASED ON BERGHAUS (2004, pp.154, 177) AND PFEFFER (2012, p.16)

	ORAL MEDIA	HANDWRITTEN MEDIA	PRINTED MEDIA	AUDIO-VISUAL MEDIA	DIGITAL MEDIA
TECHNOLOGY	- language	- script	- print	- recording	- computing
SYMBOLIC LAYER	- spoken word	- written word	- printed word	- broadcasted record	- ubiquitous code
MEDIA FORMATS, PRODUCTS	- talk	- manuscript	- book - article	- record, film - broadcast (radio, tv)	- hypertext - multimedia - program - application - social media
ACADEMIC GENRES	- -	- classical text	- research monograph - journal (article) - textbook - seminar paper, thesis	- documentary - recorded lecture	- presentation slides - research data, interactive database + application - academic software - educational ressources - social networks + virtual organizations
LAYERS OF REALITY	- yes/no-version of reality	- potential reality (maybe)	- differentiated rationalities	- recorded (as-if) reality	- computed reality
FORMS OF DISTRIBUTION	- synchronous - few-to-few	- asynchronous - few-to-few- among-many	- asynchronous - few-to-many	- asynchronous + synchronous - few-to-many	- asynchronous + synchronous - many-to-many
FORMS OF SOCIETY	- tribes	- centrally unified states	- functionally differentiated states	- global village in world society	- heterogeneous networks in world- society

However, one can also regard formal education as a system of sequential educational offerings that allows for refining literacy (and other skills and competences) gradually through several consecutive levels during an educational career. While primary education deals with the consumption of simple media products (e.g. children books) and the productions of simple texts (e.g. essays on personal experiences), secondary education deals with more complex media products (e.g. novels) and the production of more advanced texts (e.g. analytical essays). Given such a consecutive understanding of literacy, alphabetization at an academic level then could mean that universities should train the critical consumption of academic media products (e.g. research monographs or academic journals), and the skillful production of similar products (e.g. thesis or seminar papers).

Digital media literacy at an academic level

Literacy at an academic level can be defined as the ability to skillfully deal with media products and academic genres that are relevant for the respective discipline. New information and communication technologies are relevant for academia as far as they develop new media products and new academic genres.

As has been mentioned above, audio-visual media only brought minor changes to academic communication. Probably, broadcasted documentaries contribute to the popularization of the sciences. Apart from that, records and film are mainly used for the collection of research data. Sometimes, recordings and broadcasts of lectures have been produced, but at least in analogous times they often have been too ex-

pensive for their mostly specialized audience they tried to address and therefore remained a niche product.

Digital media formats and products

The situation created by digital media is fundamentally different, since their use has become an ubiquitous phenomenon. Digital media can mediate and transform every part of academic communication. They even can comprise traditional formats and academic genres, like the research monograph, the scholarly journal or the seminar paper, which are written on computers and disseminated via the internet. In these cases, not the media formats themselves have changed, but the ways in which they are produced and disseminated. Computing and its prerequisite, the binary code (0-1) have the potential to reconstruct every media format, even those originating from older technologies. Thereby, computing has the potential to serve as a ubiquitous platform for nearly all media formats and products.

However, this convergence in one single, ubiquitous symbolic layer also provides the opportunity for the emergence of new media formats and products (Table 1), such as hypertexts, which link different documents and allow for automated cross-referencing, or multimedia files, which combine formally distinct formats (e.g. print and recordings) into new arrangements. This convergence also applies to the relationship between documents and programs, or between data and algorithms, which allows for the creation of interactive applications. Last, but not least, social media can be used to create, maintain and document all sorts of relationships between different actors.

Digital genres for academia

Based on these new digital media formats, more and more new genres of scholarly communication emerge (Table 1). One of the most commonly used genres is that of academic presentation slides, which are not only used as multimedia files for supporting a physical presentation, but also for documentation and dissemination purposes (e.g. via services like Slideshare¹) beyond the live presentation itself.

Spreadsheets, databases and digital archives are important tools for research and academic work, but can easily be turned into interactive applications (e.g. Gapminder²) for the dissemination and further (often self-tailored) use of research data. Partly, the data for databases are even generated by the users of applications, e.g. via online questionnaires, self-tests, or mere metadata drawn from the traces left by users. Since the storage and the publication of digital information can be done more or less simultaneously and without much additional costs, there is increasing interest in publishing even raw data, interests that are supported by the open access and open data movement in academia, but also by public bodies and philanthropic funders of research.

Academic software is another new genre in academia. Generic examples are reference management software (e.g. Zotero³) or learning management systems (e.g. Moodle⁴). Other examples are more discipline specific and specialized, e.g. software to analyze the human genome, to calculate weather forecasts or to extract knowledge from natural languages. Software increasingly formalizes and - to a certain extent -

¹ www.slideshare.net

² www.gapminder.org

³ www.zotero.org

⁴ moodle.org

automatizes academic practices, which in many cases would not be possible without computing. Therefore, it is of crucial strategic importance to keep the knowledge about academic software in public universities, and for researchers to be able to understand, analyze and criticize the relevant algorithms.

In the past scholarly publications (e.g. monographs, journals) have been the dominant form of educational resources in higher education and little effort has been put in the development of distinct educational media products (e.g. textbooks). The interest in eLearning changed this situation and led to the emergence of a plethora of new genres for educational resources and educational applications, which in return gained significance as forms of academic publication. While this multitude of genres can partly be attributed to the diversity of academic disciplines and their respective needs, partly it has to be explained with the youth of the technology. There is still much experimentation and innovation going on, which can lead to dead ends or at least to formats of questionable sustainability. Only a few of these experiments seem to have established standards for new academic genres on a larger scale. One is the genre of the elaborated course description after the example of MIT's OpenCourseWare¹ initiative and its 280+ institutional followers in the OpenCourseWare-Consortium². The Massive Open Online Course (MOOC) might become another form of educational and media format, since many universities try to emulate this concept, which eventually may lead to its standardization and a firm establishment of this type of educational provision as a distinct genre.

Maybe the most important category of new media formats is social software. Following Mejías (2005) as quoted in McLoughlin & Lee (2008, p.13), it is possible to distinguish a wide range of different social media, which can be relevant for pedagogical purposes, e.g.:

- Virtual worlds or multi-player environments (e.g. Second life)
- Discourse facilitation systems (e.g. Email, chat)
- Content management systems (e.g. Blogs, wikis, document management systems like BSCW³)
- Peer-to-peer file sharing systems (e.g. Bittorrent, Wetransfer)
- Learning management systems (e.g. Moodle, blackboard)
- Relationship management systems (e.g. Researchgate⁴, facebook)
- Syndication systems (e.g. RSS aggregators)
- Distributed classification systems (e.g. social bookmarking sites like del.icio.us).

The high significance of social media lies in the fact that they can enable, mediate and document social relations between actors in unprecedented ways. Neither net-works, nor organizations are completely new phenomena. What is new is the reduced effort to establish relationships across long distances or to multiple actors, the increased technical potential to specify the rules of inclusion/exclusion (e.g. authentication, access rights) and the characteristics of relationships (e.g. read only, read/write, etc.), but also the increased potential to create digital manifestations of social relationships and digital documentations of processes and social interaction. It is much easier than ever before to describe the social networks of epistemic communities (e.g. via citation indices), or to create organizational relationships between remote actors (e.g. for international research projects or joint study programs across different countries). Digital manifestation and documentation of these - otherwise immaterial - social

¹ www.ocw.mit.edu

² www.oiconsortium.org

³ www.public.bscw.de

⁴ www.researchgate.net

entities makes it easier to create and manage them, but also encourages more reflection and further development of social processes.

Participating to learn

Social Media are often associated with Web 2.0, claiming that they combine content with community, and encourage a more participatory approach to dealing with media products. Many authors claim that due to these characteristics social media will fundamentally change education, the ways in which learning and teaching takes place. E.g. Brown & Adler (2008) describe this change as a paradigm shift from a Cartesian view to a social view of learning (Table 2).

TABLE 2. DIFFERENT VIEWS OF LEARNING,
BASED ON BROWN & ADLER (2008), MCLOUGHLIN & LEE (2008)

	CARTESIAN VIEW OF LEARNING	SOCIAL VIEW OF LEARNING
CONCEPT	Knowledge as substance	Knowledge as social construct
PREMISE	'I think, therefore I am'	'We participate, therefore we are'
PREFERRED KNOWLEDGE TYPE	Context-free	Niche-relevant
TYPICAL KNOWLEDGE PRODUCT	Encyclopedia Britannica	Wikipedia
TYPICAL KNOWLEDGE CREATOR	Selected expert	Trusted community member
VISIBLE, DOCUMENTED	Codified knowledge	Process of knowledge-creation
PRIORITY OF ACCESS TO LEARNING STYLE	Content	Communities
	Receptive, learning about, individual	Inquisitive, learning to be, social
STUDENT'S ROLE	Consumer	(Co-)Producer
TEACHING STYLE	Supply-push, top-down, ex-cathedra, standardized	Demand-pull, responsive, individualized
TEACHER'S ROLE	Knowledge transmitter, instructor, examiner	Knowledge + community broker, enabler, coach, reviewer
LEARNING ENVIRONMENT	Closed classroom	Open, participatory environments
GRADUATE	Autonomous problem solver	Co-worker in heterogeneous teams

In the past, universities could be characterized as locally situated, centralized and self-contained repositories of books, which also hosted professors and students (Noam 1999). This situation also determined the production structure of education, which mainly took place in closed classrooms, assigning the teacher the role as an expert, who pre-selected and centrally transmitted codified knowledge. In this Cartesian view of learning, the student was predominantly regarded as consumer and expected to develop a receptive (and reproductive) learning style.

In contrast to that, the internet has vastly expanded access to all sorts of resources, including scholarly publications and educational materials. Additionally, social soft-

ware and the Web 2.0 created open, participatory environments with many opportunities not just to consume, but also to contribute content. This blurs the lines between consumers and producers of content and shifts the focus towards a social view of learning. From this perspective, it becomes more important to regard the student as (co-)producer of content and to encourage students to develop an inquisitive learning style. Teachers should then emphasize their role as coaches of their students, enabling them to get access to (and select from) diverse knowledge resources, but also encouraging them to form, participate in and contribute to diverse groups, organizations and communities.

New skills requirements

The brief overview on digital genres for academia makes it clear that the emergence of new academic genres is far from being completed. Rather we are just at the beginning of a new area of academic production. However, it is already clear that the notion of academic literacy has to be extended to scholarly communication in digital formats as well, even if it depends largely on the respective academic discipline, which particular media products and genres are the most relevant for the discipline. Based on this overview, new emphasis has to be put on at least three types of skills, which become crucial for academic literacy:

- Skills to navigate and select relevant information from an overabundance of diverse sources available, which requires the ability to locate relevant information sources and evaluate them for quality, reliability and currency (e.g. Lorenzo & Dziuban 2006). Basic research skills and critical thinking have to be expanded from traditional to new information sources; they cannot be abolished by the algorithms of search engines.
- Skills to produce content in different media formats and genres (e.g. full text, presentation slides, abstract, metadata) for different audiences and purposes, which also involves the ability to both unfold and reduce the complexity of a topic by elaborating it in length and distilling its essence in brief. Rather than isolating different formats and genres against each other, their interrelationship and complementarity in an ecosystem of scholarly communication should be appreciated.
- Skills to participate in and to contribute to different digitally mediated social entities (e.g. small study groups, social networks, virtual organizations), which involves the ability to distinguish between different social settings implied by digital applications, but also the ability for working in these settings, for pooling knowledge, for negotiating across cultural differences of distinct communities, and for reconciling different sets of expertise (e.g. Jenkins 2009).

Educating for academic media literacy as an organizational task

To educate for academic media literacy cannot be just the task of individual teachers. Rather, education for academic media literacy has to be regarded as organizational task of higher education institutions, which offer study programs as complex and integrated products. Therefore, it is necessary to address the university as an organization, to set the education for media literacy on its agenda, and to translate this organizational objective into the structures and processes of the organization.

The following paragraphs will describe a few examples, how academic literacy can be embedded in the learning outcomes of study programs, how the training of specified ICT-skills can be implemented in across an entire curriculum, and how generic criteria for the supervision and the assessment of seminar papers and theses can foster the development of academic literacy.

Literacy in generic learning outcomes of study programs

Academic qualifications are not only at the highest level of the formal education system, there also exists a sequential (hierarchical) order among academic qualifications.

A consecutive notion for the development of knowledge, skills and competencies is ingrained in different qualification frameworks, such as the European Qualification Framework - EQF (European Parliament & Council 2008) or the Qualification Framework of the European Higher Education Area - QF-EHEA (European Ministers Responsible for Higher Education 2005), even if they do not explicitly mention literacy in their concepts. Still, the definitions of learning outcomes in national qualification frameworks sometimes touch aspects of academic literacy. The Norwegian Qualification Framework, for example, deals with aspects of literacy at sequential levels in a differentiated, consecutive way (Table 3).

TABLE 3. GENERIC LEARNING OUTCOMES DEFINING ACADEMIC LITERACY FOR CONSECUTIVE QUALIFICATIONS IN THE NORWEGIAN NQF, QUOTED FROM NOKUT (N.N.)

SKILLS	GENERAL COMPETENCE
Bachelor candidates - “can find, evaluate and refer to information and scholarly subject matter and present it in a manner that sheds light on the problem” - “masters relevant scholarly tools, techniques and forms of communication”	Bachelor candidates - “can communicate important academic subject matters such as theories, problems and solutions, both in writing and orally, as well as through other forms of communication”
Master candidates - “can analyze and deal critically with various sources of information and use them to structure and formulate scholarly arguments”	Master candidates - “can communicate extensive independent work and masters language and terminology of the academic field”
PhD candidates - “can formulate problems and carry out research and scholarly and/or artistic development work”	PhD candidates - “can communicate research and development work through recognized Norwegian and international channels”

Learning outcomes for academic literacy that have been defined at the level of the national qualification framework can be further specified and embedded in discipline specific curricula. E.g., the Bergen University College embedded literacy explicitly in the all bachelor degree description documents for its health and social sciences study program.

TABLE 4. SPECIFIED LEARNING OUTCOMES DEFINING ACADEMIC LITERACY FOR BA DEGREES IN HEALTH AND SOCIAL SCIENCES (Kavli et al., 2012)

Document section	“Learning Outcomes - General competencies”
Text	“After completing the BA degree, the candidate will be able to: - find and critically evaluate health and social science literature from quality information source - use information and cite it in his/her own work in accordance with ethical requirements and guidelines”

Detailed ICT-skills in study programs

While the two examples mentioned above mainly deal with general academic information literacy, the College of Arts and Sciences at the George Mason University elaborated a list of 10 more detailed ICT-skills, which can be more closely related to digital media products (Table 5). For its project 'Technology Across Curriculum', the college cooperated with regional employers, defining ICT-skills both at basic and more advanced level. Rather than to expand the curriculum by setting up separate courses for training these skills, this list was held against the given curriculum, trying to identify, which of the existing courses would be most appropriate to train which of the respective skills. This approach guaranteed both a close connection of skills training with content of and work in the discipline, as well as the involvement and commitment of the entire faculty with these newly defined organizational goals. The entire faculty was engaged in the process to discuss academic information literacy and ICT-skills, and in implementing them into their daily teaching routine.

TABLE 5. 10 ICT-SKILLS AT GEORGE MASON UNIVERSITY
AGEE & HOLISKY (2000)

1. communication	email and electronic collaboration in groups
2. documentation	word processing and websites
3. presentation	use of presentation technologies
4. investigation	critical use of Web resources
5. data banks	feeding and retrieving data banks
6. spread sheets	calculation and diagrams
7. statistics	descriptive statistical applications
8. graphic and multimedia	handling of graphic and multimedia files
9. law, ethics, security	copyrights, privacy, firewall, etc.
10. hard- and software	personal computer/local network, operation system/application software, document management, etc.

Criteria to assess/feedback student works or theses

Rather than focusing on the reproduction of facts or on the mere volume of written assignments, the way in which students write has to gain importance. While universities in Anglo-Saxon countries frequently offer support in academic writing for their students, continental European universities often seem to neglect this task, as if they assume, that all the training for literacy should have been completed in secondary education already. As a result, many students complete their course work without receiving much - if any - feedback on their analytical and writing skills. If students have deficits in these respects, they become obvious only at the end of their studies, when they have to produce a final thesis. Much of what should have been done throughout the entire course of studies is left to the supervisor of the final thesis.

For my personal use as a frequent supervisor of interdisciplinary seminar works and final theses, I developed a set of criteria for the analysis and evaluation, which can be applied to any kind of research related text. The criteria are based on the understanding that research has to make every step in the cognitive process explicit and transparent to allow for critique and further improvement. In this set of criteria, I distinguished between content related and formal criteria (Table 6).

This list provides me with generic criteria for the supervision of any kind of student papers and research texts in the social sciences, more or less regardless of their specific topic. They also allow for tackling selected issues in the context of a holistic assessment of a research project/text, e.g. if research goal, hypothesis and methods fit together and if they are well connected. It proved to be helpful to present and explain this list to my students before they start with their work, since it can be used as a framework to communicate my expectations in advance, and as a terminology to provide feedback, that is independent of the concrete content of the student's text.

TABLE 6. CRITERIA FOR THE SUPERVISION AND ASSESSMENT OF SEMINAR PAPERS AND THESES

CONTENT RELATED CRITERIA	FORMAL CRITERIA
Point of departure, goal Is the problem or topic of the research project/text clearly defined? Is it clear, why and for whom the problem/topic is relevant?	Completeness Does the text contain all relevant elements (e.g. author, title, abstract, introduction, conclusions, references)?
Research question & research objects Did the author formulate productive research questions? Did the author clearly define the unit(s) of observation?	Structure Does the text distinguish between major and peripheral aspects? Does the text have a main message?
Hypothesis, expected results Are assumptions (aka: theory) made explicit? Does the author define which type of results/products/claims are expected?	Ability to observe and use abstractions Does the author distinguish between observation, explanation and evaluation? Does the author develop/apply useful categories?
Approach, methods Does the author explain relevant decisions in the research process? Are the research process and the methods made transparent?	Ability to quote Does the author distinguish between different observers and observing positions, and develop his/her distinct voice in this context? Does the author attribute observation, explanation and judgment to distinct sources?
Conclusions Does the research project/text allow for conclusions and/or recommendations? Can the research questions be answered?	Argumentation Is the author able to develop an argument? Does the author explain the relationship between different statements or elements of the text (e.g. between assumptions and data)?
Consistency, common thread Do the distinct elements (point of departure, research questions and unit of observation, expected results, methods and conclusions) fit together?	

Conclusion

As has been argued throughout this paper, academic literacy can be defined as the ability to deal with media products and academic genres that are relevant for the respective discipline. This ability comprises both the critical consumption and the skillful production of media products. Educating for academic literacy should not be regarded as an unpleasant obligation, but rather as a core task of higher education institutions, a task that requires organizational responses. This task has largely been forgotten and has to be reemphasized.

The emergence of new digital formats and genres of academic communication complicate this task, since they disrupt traditional production structures and processes in higher education. However, digital formats and genres do not abolish the need for basic research skills and rigorous, critical thinking. Rather, the emergence of new digital knowledge resources and environments force scholars and higher

education institutions to reexamine their traditional information sources and publication practices, and to consider, which new digital sources and practices have become relevant for the respective discipline. Academia and higher education is forced to become more self-reflective and self-critical than ever before.

Last, but not least, the student as co-producer of content, but also as a partner and co-producer of education has to be re-established, or maybe re-invented as well. Traditional universities regarded students as apprentices, which had to be introduced to the community of scholars, and therefore had to be involved in scholarly communication of the respective discipline. Massification of higher education damaged this concept and shifted the focus of education from learning to teaching. Digital media provide the opportunity to establish a new kind of student-centered approach, an approach that puts the student's ability to communicate and produce content in the focus of educational activities.

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